

**NEGATIVE PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS AND ONLINE
SHOPPING BEHAVIOUR: A REVIEW AMONG COLLEGE
STUDENTS' AT TONGREN CITY IN CHINA**

Zhang Zhong Yangⁱ,

Jacqueline Tham,

S. M. Ferdous Azam

Postgraduate Centre (PGC),

Management and Science University,

University Drive, Off Persiaran Olahraga,

40100 Shah Alam, Selangor,

Malaysia

Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to determine the negative psychological factors and online shopping behaviour. This is a review paper among college students' at Tongren city in China. This study will significantly contribute in dealing with challenges that are prevailing in the e-commerce market, and online retailers have to understand E-commerce market, buyers' behaviour and to consider all factors that will affect online shopping in order to develop better strategies to retain existing customers and attract more potential buyers. Consumer buying behaviour is affected by many variables, ranging from personal motivations, needs, attitudes and values, socioeconomic and cultural values, age, gender, professional status to social influences of various kinds exerted by family, friends, colleagues and society as a whole (Solomon, 2004). Studying various factors affecting online shopping will help online retailers to understand the association between factors and consumer buying behaviour. In this context, research is aimed to study the various factors affecting negative psychological factors affecting online shopping among college students in Tongren University.

Keywords: negative psychological factors, online shopping behaviour, college students', Tongren city, China

ⁱ Correspondence: email 38721736@qq.com

1. Introduction

Online shopping is no longer a new phenomenon in many emerging and developed countries which has assisted in offering low cost and convenient shopping solutions to the traditionally unreachable market through the use for internet technology and Information Communication Technologies (ICTs) (Kasaje & Charira, 2012). According to Laukkanen and Lauronen (2012), online shopping has shown a phenomenal growth for the past years. The services of online shopping can also improve operational performance and increase the amount of data processing (Rizwan et al., 2014; Azam and Moha Asri, 2015; Tham et al., 2017; Udriyah et al., 2019; Al Shehhi and Azam, 2019a; Tao et al., 2019). Companies around the world have modified their strategies to better reach out to their customers, and the rapid growth of the economy is based on smart online shopping that is primarily based on the internet, computer systems and cell phones (Rizwan et al., 2015). Visual perception of products in online shops is the key to customers' responses (Jarvenpaa and Todd, 1996; Szymanski and Hise, 2000; Haque et al., 2014; Rachmawati et al., 2019; Tarofder et al., 2019; Al Shehhi and Azam, 2019b). Products in online shops are commonly depicted in isolation, such that that the product depictions are cut out from the background and appear without any shadows (e.g., on amazon.com and ikea.com). Amazon, for example, requires products to be depicted individually, against a white background which (i.e. the picture frame contains neither a shadow nor anything else). Because Amazon serves as an example for other online shops, isolated product depictions are the de facto standard for product depictions used in most online shops (Amazon, 2018). This common practice has several advantages. First, photo production for hidden objects is easy, fast and cheap. Second, showing products in isolation is space-saving and allows online shops to place more products in the customer's field of view, which is assumed to increase the number of products which are seen by a customer (Chitika, 2013; Flosi et al., 2013; Song and Kim, 2012). Third, depictions without a background have low visual complexity and high contrast, which is both, associated with more positive judgements and increased attention (Pieters et al., 2010; Reber et al., 1998). Despite this advantage, products presented in isolation without a background may have unintended adverse effects, not least because such product depictions do not occur in the real world (Bar, 2004; Azam et al., 2014; Haur et al., 2017; Tarofder et al., 2017; Katukurunda et al., 2019; Chong et al., 2019).

Since the China Open Door Policy 1978, to attract foreign talents, China has seen an increase in Foreigners coming to China. China used to be known as a tourist destination with people fascinated with Culture and Chinese food, but foreigners now come to China for different reasons. Online Purchasing Behaviour has attracted the interests of scholars Mosteller, Donthu, and Eroglu (2014). There is a need to further understand the online purchasing behaviour of consumers, San Martín and Herrero (2012). With the growing number of international students in China, one cannot simply ignore that it is indeed a niche market and calls for study. The focus of this study is to examine international students' online shopping behaviour in China critically. The

previous study in China has focused on Online Shopping adoption by Chinese consumers (Clemes, Gan, & Zhang, 2014). Other studies have also focused on Chinese students online shopping attitude and gender differences in the influence of online communication on e-commerce purchase decision strategies Chai et al., (2016) but neglect the emerging role of international students in the markets. Thus, this study seeks to understand the factors that influence their online shopping behaviour. In a Dual Country Perspective study between the U.S and Irish Students, Comegys and Brennan (2003) find that language has an impact on online shopping, so it is essential in this study that to find out to what extent of negative psychological factors of online shopping behaviour among college students' in Tongren City, China.

Purchases of online shopping in China retrieves information on products and services through the text, video introduction, specifications and picture information of the goods through the Internet e-commerce platform and sends out the purchase request through the electronic order, then fills in the private information (name, communication, address, contact, etc.) sellers or vendors in the e-commerce platform (Jayasuriya and Azam, 2017; Dewi et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2019; Kanapathipillai and Azam, 2019; Gunasinghe et al., 2019). This information was then receiving the purchase requests, conclude the purchase agreements, and determine payment terms. Buyers use online payment methods on the platform, which consist of online bank transfer, AliPay transfer and Counter transfer, which is also known as bank transfer desk.

The emergence of the Internet and communication technology makes electronic commerce possible. Since the 20th century, the rapid development of the Internet and communication technology has made e-commerce enter a new stage. With the establishment and perfection of Taobao, Tmall, Jingdong, Victoria products, Alipay and other e-commerce platforms and online payment platforms, online shopping is gradually emerging. Meanwhile, with the rapid popularization of mobile Internet and the gradual improvement of mobile payment means, online shopping has quietly changed the social business structure and lifestyle. Today, online shopping is being a preferred choice due to time-saving and convenience and has been giving ease in consumers' preference.

According to the Ministry of Education, the number of college students in China has been increasing since 2012, reaching 324.32 million in 2017. They are not only one of the central bodies of online shopping at present, but also have independent online shopping consciousness and characteristics. On the one hand, they have strong online shopping demand and relatively advanced online shopping consumption concept; on the other hand, they are at a disadvantage in occupying social resources, their economic ability is not yet independent, and their online shopping ability is not yet independent. It is subject to significant constraints. These two contradictions make their online shopping behaviour has many problems, which eventually lead to excessive consumption or debt, and bring about problems in real life, such as "bare loans" and "violent collection", which cause widespread concern in society, and seriously endanger the physical and mental health, learning and development of College students. College

students are a group formed under the background of receiving higher education. In order to complete their socialization, they focus on learning and make themselves thrive. This research is mainly aimed at college students in Tongren City, involving two colleges and universities, namely Tongren College and Tongren Vocational and Technical College. The subjects involved are mathematics, information science and system science, physics, chemistry, biology, psychology, agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry and veterinary science, aquaculture and clinical medicine. Science, Material Science, Electronic Communication and Automatic Control Technology, Computer Science and Technology, Chemical Engineering, Food Science and Technology, Civil Engineering, Water Conservancy Engineering, Marxism, Philosophy, Linguistics, Literature, Art, History, Economics, Law, Sociology, Ethnology and Culture, Journalism and Biography Broadcasting, Education and Sports Science [National Standard for Classification and Code of First-Class Disciplines (GB/T 13745-2009)].

2. Review of the Literature

The study on “The influence of negative psychological factors on College Students’ online shopping behaviour” is still at its infant stage in China. Based on the above factors, this paper mainly adopts the methods of literature research, questionnaire survey, empirical research and statistical analysis to correct college students in Tongren City. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) were used to explain the concept for these studies.

2.1 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

This study is mainly empirical research, not trying to establish a new model, using a mature UTAUT model, in order to achieve twice the result with half the effort. UTAUT model is one of the eight main technology acceptance theories that Venkatesh, Morris and other scholars use for reference: technology adaptation model (TTF), innovation diffusion theory (IDT), rational behaviour theory (TRA), planning behaviour theory (TPB), motivation model (MM), compound TAM and TPB model (C-TAM-TPB), PC utilization model (MPCU), social cognitive theory (SCT). Based on behavioural willingness theory, a more comprehensive and perfect model, UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology), is put forward. UTAUT divides variables into two categories by reintegrating previous model arguments. One is the core variables, including performance expectation, effort expectation, social impact and promotion conditions; the other is the intermediate variables that have a significant impact on the core variables, including gender, age, volunteerism and experience. Source variables of performance expectation include perceived usefulness, job adaptability and achievement expectation, which are used to indicate the extent to which individuals think that using the system is helpful to their work. Source variables of effort expectation include perceived ease of use and complexity, which are used to represent how much effort an

individual thinks it takes to use the system. Subdividing source variables of social impact include compatibility of social factors, which are used to represent the degree of individual perception affected by surrounding groups. Source variables of facilitation conditions include facilitation conditions and behavioural control perception, which are used to characterize the degree of support of individual perception organizations for the use of systems in related technologies and devices. Behaviour intention directly determines the use of behaviour, while performance expectation, effort expectation and social impact affect the use of behaviour indirectly through affecting behaviour intention. The original model of UTAUT is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1: Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)
(Source: Venkatesh et al., 2003)

This study examines a set of research hypotheses based on quantitative data collected from questionnaires in order to establish a theory to verify the hypothesis, rather than trying to establish a theory. Therefore, quantitative methods are considered to be more suitable for this study. It mainly adopts technology to adopt and utilize integration theory, namely the UTAUT model (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, UTAUT). Besides, this study establishes the model trend of theoretical research, which is in good agreement with the UTAUT model (technology adoption and utilization integration theory). Therefore, the UTAUT model (technology adoption and utilization integration theory) is adopted in this study. In this study, independent variables include their negative psychological factors, negative psychological factors related to commodities, negative psychological factors related to negative social

consumption concepts, and non-independent variables are college students' online shopping behaviour under the influence of negative psychological factors, including emotional online shopping and comparative online shopping. In online shopping, the intermediate variables are gender and disposable living expenses. The relationship between variables: under the influence of negative psychological factors, resulting in harmful online shopping behaviour will eventually result in excessive consumption or debt. In the purchase process, some harmful online shopping behaviour is affected by disposable living expenses.

3. Material and Method

This research is based on the investigation of "the influence of negative psychological factors on College Students' online shopping behaviour". It mainly studies the online shopping behaviour of college students in Tongren City, including emotional online shopping and comparative online shopping. It also investigates whether there are negative psychological factors in online shopping. There are three kinds of psychological states: negative psychological factors related to purchases of products and services and negative psychological factors related to negative social consumption concepts.

Since this is an academic paper, so the relationship between negative psychological factors and college students' online purchasing behaviour is mainly manifested by negative psychological factors due to self-awareness, the convenience of online shopping and varieties of offers, and due to social influence.

4. Findings and Discussion

The negative psychological factor of oneself is empty psychology. It refers to all the blanks in one's spiritual world, without belief, sustenance and boredom. In this psychological state, taking the possession and enjoyment of the online shopping process and online shopping consumer goods as a means to make up for the spiritual emptiness, an emotional online shopping line will emerge. When this behaviour is seriously morbid and unable to control its purchase behaviour, it is not too much related to the number of free-living expenses as an addictive online shopping.

The purpose of this study is to study the influence of negative psychological factors on College Students' online purchasing behaviour. For this reason, negative psychological factors (mainly including their negative psychological factors, negative psychological factors related to commodities, negative psychological factors related to negative social consumption concepts) are set as independent variables. Online shopping behaviour (including emotional online shopping and comparative online shopping) is a non-independent variable, while the discretionary cost of living is the intermediate variable. Finally, the negative consequences of excessive consumption or debt are formed. According to the UTAUT model theory, the influence of satisfying research negative psychological factors on College Students' online shopping behaviour is

constructed (Maghfuriyah et al., 2019; Pushpakumara et al., 2019; Al Shehhi and Azam, 2019c). The negative psychological factors related to the negative consumption concept of the society: the purchase motivation under the guidance of conformity psychology has the following nature, often manifested as group buying. Purchasing behaviour has the characteristics of aimlessness, contingency and impulse. Alternatively, the purpose of consumption is to satisfy curiosity and not to lag. The purchasing motivation under the guidance of conspicuous psychology is vanity, which is often manifested in the purchase of expensive goods, favourite goods and fashionable goods. Its purchasing behaviour has the characteristics of comparability and advance.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

College students are an essential component of society. Their online shopping behaviour is influenced by social consumption ideology. There is a widespread phenomenon of online shopping beyond their economic affordability in Tongren. Given this phenomenon, this paper mainly studies the impulsive online shopping, conformity online shopping, comparison online shopping, addiction online shopping and other purchasing behaviours of Tongren College Students under the influence of negative psychological factors, such as conformity psychology, comparison psychology (showing off psychology) and race psychology. Considering the leading role rate of various negative psychological factors in the online shopping process, this paper puts forward reasonable suggestions, which can correct and guide college students' wrong online shopping behaviour.

Prior research on product displays has examined background colour and contrast effects on customers' affective responses (Grobelny & Michalski, 2015; Im & Ha, 2011; Michalski & Grobelny, 2016; Schifferstein et al., 2017). Research also demonstrated that a typical scene that contains other semantically related objects positively affects customer behaviour (Shapiro, 1999; Yoo & Kim, 2014). However, research in this domain has not considered whether the absence of a background which is typical in isolated product depictions hurts customers' affective and behavioural responses (De Silva et al., 2017; Kuruwitaarachchi et al., 2019; Pambreni et al., 2019; Fernando et al., 2019). This is particularly surprising as Kahn (2017) stresses that the way products are depicted individually and as assortments in online shops play an essential role in efficient processing and influencing customers' perception and liking. Importantly, Kahn (2017) emphasized the central role of processing fluency in the context of online product depictions. Although there is growing research on visual perception in the consumer behaviour domain (e.g., Demangeot and Broderick, 2010; Lam et al., 2007; Pieters and Wedel, 2004, 2012; Wedel et al., 2008), only a few studies considered visual processing fluency in isolated product displays, and none considered its antecedents and consequences effects consumers spending behaviour (e.g., Leonhardt et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2016). The scarce literature in this area has demonstrated that product images that

face the centre of a print or online advertisement are more fluent in engaging responses from online consumers (Leonhardt et al., 2015).

Similarly, horizontally displayed products are more comfortable to process than vertical product displays because the human field of view is more full in the horizontal than in the vertical direction (Deng et al., 2016). In 1991, China launched the application of EDI (Electronic Data Exchange) in the departments of customs, foreign trade, transportation and shipping, and initiated the process of gold cards, customs and taxes. In 1996, the Ministry of Foreign Trade established the China International Electronic Commerce Center.

With the popularity of the Internet, online shopping has gradually changed from a new thing to a part of people's daily life, impacting people's traditional consumption habits and thinking, lifestyle, and gradually penetrated the hearts of the people with its unique advantages. E-commerce model, which takes online shopping as a typical representative, has a tremendous impact on consumers and enterprises. For consumers, compared with traditional sales channels, e-commerce mode can provide more convenient purchase experience without time and space constraints, expand the range of varieties available to consumers, and facilitate consumers to select more affordable products. Such a convenient way of online shopping has changed from the possible state to the most popular, most suitable for young people to buy a way of shopping.

College students are mainly born after 1990, with age ranges from 18 to 24. The popularity of computers and mobile phones has reached 100%. The growth environment differs significantly from that of the previous generation. They are more adapted to the Internet ecology and are the most sensitive people to the Internet. Online shopping, a convenient and fast form of shopping, has also been accepted by many people. Young generations are more accustomed to the very convenient consumption mode of e-commerce, and, accept online shopping behaviour very quickly, and have formed a particular climate in them. Moreover, the convenience and immateriality of mobile payment and Internet payment weaken their monetary concept and form their more modern online shopping concept.

On the other hand, the extensive promotion of the network financial institutions themselves has also made young people more aware of the network financial business. Considering the characteristics of young people's impulsiveness, advanced personality and low disposable income, a large number of financial planning schemes have been put forward, which have increased college students' idea of enjoying future life ahead of time and overdrawn future funds, seriously affecting college students' online shopping behaviour.

In recent years, harmful online shopping behaviour has shown a variety of phenomena. By comparing the relevant information and survey summary, the types of online shopping behaviour of college students are emotional online shopping and comparative online shopping. The main psychological factors that cause these two phenomena are their negative psychological factors, negative psychological factors

related to commodities, and negative psychological factors related to negative social consumption concept.

References

- Al Shehhi and Azam, S. M. F. (2019a). Total Quality Management and Project Management towards Organisational Success of Agriculture and Fisheries in Sultanate of Oman: A Measurement Model, *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 4 (1): 1-17
- Al Shehhi and Azam, S. M. F. (2019b). Developing and Validating the TQM Framework in the Sultanate of Oman Agriculture and Fisheries Context, *European Journal of Economic and Financial Research*, 3(4): 30-42
- Al Shehhi and Azam, S. M. F. (2019c). Measuring the Mediating Role of Project Management between Total Quality Management and Organisational Success in Sultanate of Oman, *European Journal of Human Resource Management Studies*, 2(2): 45-58
- Alter, A. L. and D. M. Oppenheimer (2009). Uniting the tribes of fluency to form a metacognitive nation. *Personality and Social Psychology Review* 13 (3), 219–235.
- Amazon (2018). Product Image Requirements. URL: <https://www.amazon.com/gp/help/customer/display.html?nodeId=200109520> (visited on 04/06/2018).
- Anesbury, Z., Nenycz-Thiel, M., Dawes, J. And Kennedy, R. 2015. How do shoppers behave online? An observational study of online grocery shopping. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour* 15: 1–11.
- Azam, S. M. F. and Moha Asri A. (2015). Differential Roles between Owner and Manager in Financial Practice That Contributes to Business Success: An Analysis on Malaysian Small Business, *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 4 (1 S2): 123-134
- Azam, S. M. F., Haque, A., Sarwar, A. and Anwar, N. (2014). Training Program Effectiveness of Service Initiators: Measuring Perception of Female Employees of Bank Using Logistic Approach, *Asian Research Journal of Business Management*, 1 (2): 98-108
- Babin, L. A. and A. C. Burns, (1997). Effects of print ad pictures and a copy contains instructions to imagine on the mental imagery that mediates attitudes. *Journal of Advertising* 26 (3), 33–44.
- Brylla and Walsh / Isolated Product Depictions Twenty-Sixth European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS2018), Portsmouth, UK, 2018 13
- Brylla and Walsh / Isolated Product Depictions Twenty-Sixth European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS2018), Portsmouth, UK, 2018 15
- Castiello, U. (2001). Implicit processing of shadows. *Vision Research* 41 (18), 2305–2309.

- Cavazza, N. and V. Gabrielli (2015). Affordant shapes of product holder influence product evaluation and purchase intention. *Current Psychology* 34 (2), 447–465.
- Cerny, C. A. And Kaiser, H. F. (1977). A study of a measure of sampling adequacy for factor-analytic correlation matrices. *Multivariate Behavioural Research*, 12(1): 43–47.
- Chaffey, D. (2018). Ecommerce conversion rates. URL: <https://www.smartinsights.com/ecommerce/ecommerce-analytics/ecommerce-conversion-rates/> (visited on 04/05/2018).
- Chai, C., et al., (2016) Gender differences in the effect of communication on college students' online decisions. *Computers in Human Behaviour*. 65: p. 176-188.
- Childers, T. L., Carr, C. L., Peck, J. And Carson, S., (2001). Hedonic and utilitarian motivations for online retail shopping behaviour. *Journal of Retailing*, 77(4): 511–535.
- Chitika, (2013). The Value of Google Result Positioning. URL: <https://chitika.com/google-positioningvalue> (visited on 11/30/2017).
- Chong, P. L., Ong, T. S., Abdullah, A. and Choo, W. C. (2019). Internationalisation and Innovation on Balanced Scorecard (BSC) among Malaysian Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), *Management Science Letters*, 9(10): 1617–1632
- Citrin, A. V., Stem, D., Spangenberg, E. R. And Clarck, M. J., (2003). Consumer need for tactile input: an internet retailing challenge. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(11): 915–922.
- Clemes, M. D., C. Gan, and J. Zhang (2014). An empirical analysis of online shopping adoption in Beijing, China. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 21(3): p. 364-375.
- Comegys, C. and M. L. Brennan (2003). Students' online shopping behaviour: A dual-country perspective. *Journal of Internet Coulter*, K. S. and A. L. Roggeveen, (2014). Price number relationships and deal processing fluency: The effects of approximation sequences and number multiples. *Journal of Marketing Research* 51 (1), 69–82.
- Darley, W. K., Blankson, C. and Luethge, D. J. (2010). Toward an integrated framework for online consumer behaviour and decision-making process: A review. *Psychology & Marketing*, 2(27): 94–116.
- Davenport, J. L. (2007). Consistency effects between objects in scenes. *Memory & Cognition* 35 (3), 393–401.
- De Graef, P., Christiaens, D., and G. d'Ydewalle (1990). Perceptual effects of scene context on object identification. *Psychological Research* 52 (4), 317–329.
- De Silva, A. D. A., Khatibi, A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2017). Do the Demographic Differences Manifest in Motivation to Learn Science and Impact on Science Performance? Evidence from Sri Lanka, *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 16(S1), 47–67
- Demangeot, C. and A. J. Broderick (2010). Consumer perceptions of online shopping environments: A gestalt approach. *Psychology & Marketing* 27 (2), 117–140.

- Deng, X., Kahn, B. E., Unnava, H. R., and H. Lee (2016). A 'wide' variety: Effects of horizontal versus vertical display on assortment processing, perceived variety, and choice. *Journal of Marketing Research* 53 (5), 682-698.
- Dewi, N, Azam, S. M. F. and Yusoff, S. K. M. (2019). Factors influencing the information quality of local government financial statement and financial accountability, *Management Science Letters*, 9 (9): 1373-1384.
- Elder, R. S. and A. Krishna (2012). The "visual depiction effect" in advertising: Facilitating embodied mental simulation through product orientation. *Journal of Consumer Research* 38 (6), 988– 1003.
- Engel, J. F., Blackwell, R. D. And Miniard, P. W. (1986). *Consumer behaviour*. 5th Edition. Hinsdale, IL: Dryden. EUROSTAT. 2004. Internet purchases by individuals. [Online]. Available at: <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do> [Accessed: 2018, January 8].
- Epstein, R. and N. Kanwisher (1998). A cortical representation of the local visual environment. *Nature* 392, 598–601.
- Etkin, J. and C. Mogilner (2016). Does variety among activities increase happiness? *Journal of Consumer Research* 43 (2), 210–229. Field, A. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics*. London, UK: Sage.
- Eurostat (2017). Digital economy & society in the EU: A browse through our online world in figures [Online]. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/infographs/ict/bloc-2a.html> [Accessed: 2018, January 8].
- Fernando, W. H. M., Yusoff, S. K. M, Khatibi, A. and Azam S. M. F. (2019). A Review on Human Capital; Two Principal Ideas Predominantly Generic Human Capital and Specific Human Capital for Organizational Performance. *European Journal of Economic and Financial Research*, 3(5): 35-47
- Flosi, S., Fulgoni, G., and A. Vollman (2013). If an advertisement runs online and no one sees it, is it still an ad? *Journal of Advertising Research* 53 (2), 192–199.
- Friedman, A. (1979). Framing pictures: The role of knowledge in automatized encoding and memory for gist. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* 108 (3), 316–355.
- Grobelny, J. and R. Michalski (2015). The role of background color, interletter spacing, and font size on preferences in the digital presentation of a product. *Computers in Human Behaviour* 43, 85–100.
- Gunasinghe, A., Hamid, J. A., Khatibi, A. and Azam S. M. F. (2019). Academicians' Acceptance of Online Learning Environments: A Review of Information System Theories and Models. *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, 19 (1-H): 30-39
- Hair, J., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M. And Sarstedt, M. 2017. *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling*. 2nd Edition. Los Angeles: Sage.

- Hand, C., Riley, F. D., Harris, P., Singh, J. And Rettie, R. (2009). Online grocery shopping: the influence of situational factors. *European Journal of Marketing*, 43(9): 1205–1219.
- Haque A., Sarwar, A., Azam, S. M. F. and Yasmin, F. (2014), Total Quality Management Practices in the Islamic Banking Industry: Comparison between Bangladesh and Malaysian Islamic Bank, *International Journal of Ethics in Social Sciences*, 2 (1): 5-18.
- Harel, A., Kravitz, D. J., and C. I. Baker (2013). Deconstructing visual scenes in cortex: Gradients of the object and spatial layout information. *Cerebral Cortex* 23 (4), 947–957.
- Haur, C. H., Khatibi, A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2017), Antecedents of Consumers' Perception towards Online Advertising in Malaysia: The Structure Equation Modeling Approach, *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 2 (3): 15-30
- Hayes, A. F. (2013). Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach. New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Henderson, J. M. (2003). Human gaze control during real-world scene perception. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 7 (11), 498–504.
- Henderson, J. M. (2005). Introduction to real-world scene perception. *Visual Cognition* 12 (6), 849– 851.
- Henderson, J. M. and A. Hollingworth (1999). High-level scene perception, *Annual Review of Psychology* 50 (1), 243–271.
- Henderson, J. M. and F. Ferreira (2004). Scene perception for psycholinguists. In: the interface of language, vision, and action: Eye movements and the visual world. Ed. by J. M. Henderson and F. Ferreira. New York, NY: Psychology Press, pp. 1–58.
- Hickey, C., Kaiser, D., and M. V. Peelen (2015). Reward guides attention to object categories in real world scenes. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* 144 (2), 264–273.
- Huang, Y. And Oppewal, H. (2006). Why consumers hesitate to shop online: An experimental choice analysis of grocery shopping and the role of delivery fees. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 35(4/5): 334–353.
- Im, H. and Y. Ha (2011). The effect of perceptual fluency and enduring involvement on situational involvement in an online apparel shopping context. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal* 15 (3), 345–362.
- Im, H., Lennon, S. J., and L. Stoel (2010). The perceptual fluency effect on pleasurable online shopping experience. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing* 4 (4), 280–295.
- Jarvenpaa, S. L. and P. A. Todd (1996). Consumer reactions to electronic shopping on the world wide web. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce* 1 (2), 59–88.
- Kahn, B. E. (2017). Using visual design to improve customer perceptions of online assortments. *Journal of Retailing* 93 (1), 29–42.
- Jayasuriya, N. A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2017). *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 7(5), 178-183.

- Jiang, Z. and I. Benbasat (2007). Research note—investigating the influence of the functional mechanisms of online product presentations. *Information Systems Research* 18 (4), 454–470.
- Justice (2013). Tesco Stores ČR, A.S. Report. Veřejný rejstřík a Sbírka listin. [Online]. Available at: <https://or.justice.cz/ias/ui/vypis-sl-firma?subjektId=1325> [Accessed: 2018, January 19]. JUSTICE. 2014. Koloniál.cz and košík.cz foundation agreement. Veřejný rejstřík a Sbírka listin. [Online]. Available at: <https://or.justice.cz/ias/ui/rejstrik-firma.vysledky?subjektId=867236&typ=PLATNY> [Accessed: 2018, January 19].
- Kacen, J. J., Hess, J. D. And Chiang, W. K. 2013. Bricks or Clicks? Consumer Attitudes toward Traditional Stores and Online Stores. *Global Economics and Management Review*, 18(1): 12–21.
- Kahneman, D. (2003). A perspective on judgment and choice: mapping bounded rationality. *American Psychologist* 58 (9), 697–720.
- Kämäräinen, V., Saranen, J. and Holmström, J. (2001). The reception box impact on home delivery efficiency in the e-grocery business. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 31(6): 414–426. Consumers' Decision-Making in Online Grocery Shopping: The Impact of Services Offered and... 1247
- Kanapathipillai, K. and Azam S. M. F. (2019). A Conceptual Understanding of the Critical Factors That Induce Women Entrepreneurial Success In The Klang Valley, Malaysia, *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 4(2): 90-110
- Katukurunda, K. G. W. K., Yajid, S. M. A, Khatibi, A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2019). Students' Satisfaction towards Biosystems Technology; Does Programme Quality Matters? (Evidence from Sri Lankan Perspectives), *European Journal of Open Education and E-learning Studies*, 3 (2): 174-190.
- Kondo, Y., Suzuki, M., Mugikura, S., Abe, N., Takahashi, S., Iijima, T., and T. Fujii, (2005). Changes in brain activation associated with the use of a memory strategy: A functional MRI study. *Neuroimage* 24 (4), 1154–1163. Lam, S. Y., Chau, A. W. L., and T. J. Wong (2007). Thumbnails as online product displays: how consumers process them, *Journal of Interactive Marketing* 21 (1), 36–59.
- Kurnia, S., Chien, J. A. W. And Westarp, F. (2003). The Acceptance of Online Grocery Shopping. In: Proceedings of 16th Bled eCommerce Conference eTransformation. University of Maribor, 9–11 June. Slovenia: Faculty of Organizational Sciences, University of Maribor, pp. 219 -233.
- Kuruwitaarachchi, N., Yajid, S. M. A, Khatibi, A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2019). Enhance the use of Internet Based Advanced Communication Technologies in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Sri Lanka, *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 3 (2): 44-57
- Lam, S. Y., Fu, H. Y., and D. Li (2017). The influence of thematic product displays on consumers: An elaboration-based account. *Psychology & Marketing* 34 (9), 868–883.

- Landwehr, J. R., Labroo, A. A., and A. Herrmann (2011). Gut liking for the ordinary: incorporating design fluency improves automobile sales forecasts. *Marketing Science* 30 (3), 416–429.
- Lantos, G. P. (2015). *Consumer Behaviour in Action: Real-life Applications for Marketing Managers*. New York: Routledge.
- Likert, R., 1932. A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of psychology*, 140(33): 1–55.
- Lee, A. Y. and A. A. Labroo (2004). The effect of conceptual and perceptual fluency on brand evaluation. *Journal of Marketing Research* 41 (2), 151–165.
- Leonhardt, J. M., Catlin, J. R., and D. M. Pirouz (2015). Is your product facing the ad's center? facing direction affects processing fluency and ad evaluation. *Journal of Advertising* 44 (4), 315–325.
- Lepkowska-White, E., Brashear, T. G., and M. G. Weinberger (2003). A test ad appeal effectiveness in Poland and the united states: The interplay of appeal, product, and culture. *Journal of Advertising* 32 (3), 57–66.
- Li, H., Daugherty, T., and F. Biocca (2002). Impact of 3-d advertising on product knowledge, brand attitude, and purchase intention: the mediating role of presence. *Journal of Advertising* 31 (3), 43– 57. Brylla and Walsh / Isolated Product Depictions Twenty-Sixth European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS2018),
- Maghfuriyah, A., Azam, S. M. F. and Shukri, S. (2019). Market Structure and Islamic Banking Performance in Indonesia: An Error Correction Model, *Management Science Letters*, 9 (9): 1407-1418
- Malcolm, G. L., and S. Shomstein (2015). Object-based attention in real-world scenes. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* 144 (2), 257–263.
- Mandel, N. and E. J. Johnson (2002). When web pages influence choice: Effects of visual primes on experts and novices. *Journal of Consumer Research* 29 (2), 235–245.
- McDowell, W. C., Wilson, R. C., and C. O. Kile Jr (2016). An examination of retail website design and conversion rate. *Journal of Business Research* 69 (11), 4837–4842.
- Meyers-Levy, J. and L. A. Peracchio (1995). Understanding the effects of colour: How the correspondence between available and required resources affects attitudes. *Journal of Consumer Research* 22 (2), 121–138.
- Michalski, R., and J. Grobelny (2016). The effects of background colour, shape and dimensionality on purchase intentions in a digital product presentation. In: *Universal Access in Human-Computer Interaction. Users and Context Diversity*. Ed. by M. Antona and C. Stephanidis. UAHCI 2016. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 9739. Springer, pp. 468–479.
- Moe, W. W., and P. S. Fader (2004). Dynamic conversion behaviour at e-commerce sites. *Management Science* 50 (3), 326–335.
- Milkman, K. L., Rogers, T. And Bazerman, M. H. (2010). I will have the ice cream soon and the vegetables later: A study of online grocery purchases and order lead time. *Marketing Letters*, 21(1): 17–35.

- Morganosky, M. A. And Brenda, J. C. (2000). Consumer response to online grocery shopping. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 28(1): 17–26.
- Mosteller, J., N. Donthu, and S. Eroglu, (2014). The fluent online shopping experience. *Journal of Business Research*, 67(11): p. 2486-2493.
- Nguyen, H. N., Tham, J, Khatibi, A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2019). Enhancing the Capacity of Tax Authorities and its Impact on Transfer Pricing Activities of FDI Enterprises in Ha Noi, Ho Chi Minh, Dong Nai, and Binh Duong Province of Vietnam, *Management Science Letters*, 9 (8): 1299-1310
- Oliva, A. (2005). Gist of the scene. In: *The Neurobiology of Attention*. Ed. by: L. Itti, G. Rees, and J. K. Tsotsos. New York, NY: Elsevier. pp. 251–257.
- Oliva, A. and A. Torralba (2007). The role of context in object recognition. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 11 (12), 520–527.
- Orth, U. R. and R. C. Crouch (2014). Is a beauty in the aisles of the retailer? Package processing in visually complex contexts. *Journal of Retailing* 90 (4), 524–537.
- Orth, U. R. and J. Wirtz (2014). Consumer processing of interior service environments. The interplay among visual complexity, processing fluency, and attractiveness. *Journal of Service Research* 17 (3), 296–309.
- Pambreni, Y., Khatibi, A., Azam, S. M. F. and Tham, J. (2019). The Influence of Total Quality Management toward Organization Performance, *Management Science Letters*, 9 (9): 1397-1406.
- Park, J., Lennon, S. J., and L. Stoel (2005). On-line product presentation: effects on mood, perceived risk, and purchase intention. *Psychology & Marketing* 22 (9), 695–719.
- Peck, J. and S. B. Shu (2009). The effect of mere touch on perceived ownership. *Journal of Consumer Research* 36 (3), 434–447.
- Peng, X., Wang, X., and H. H. Teo (2017). Touch makes you think concretely: The effects of computer interfaces on product evaluation. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS)*, <http://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2017/HCI/Presentations/10/>.
- Pieters, R. and M. Wedel (2004). Attention capture and transfer in advertising: Brand, pictorial, and text-size effects, *Journal of Marketing* 68 (2), 36–50.
- Pieters, R. and M. Wedel (2008). Informativeness of eye movements for visual marketing. in: *Visual Marketing: From Attention to Action*. Ed. by: M. Wedel and R. Pieters. New York, NY: Lawrence Erlbaum, pp. 43–71
- Pieters, R., and M. Wedel (2012). Ad gist: Ad communication in a single eye fixation. *Marketing Science* 31 (1), 59–73.
- Pieters, R., Wedel, M., and R. Batra (2010). The stopping power of advertising: measures and effects of visual complexity. *Journal of Marketing* 74 (5), 48–60.
- Portsmouth, UK, 2018 14 Malcolm, G. L., Groen, I. I., and C. I. Baker (2016). Making sense of real-world scenes. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 20 (11), 843–856.
- Pushpakumara, W. D. H., Atan, H., Khatib, A., Azam, S. M. F. and Tham, J. (2019). Developing a Framework for Scrutinizing Strategic Green Orientation and

- Organizational Performance with Relevance to the Sustainability of Tourism Industry, *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 4 (3): 1-18
- Rachmawati, D., Shukri, S., Azam, S. M. F. and Khatibi, A. (2019). Factors Influencing Customers' Purchase Decision of Residential Property in Selangor, Malaysia, *Management Science Letters*, 9 (9): 1341-1348
- Ramus, K. And Nielsen, N. A. (2005). Online grocery retailing: what do consumers think? *Internet Research*, 15(3): 335–352.
- Robinson, H., Dall'olmo R., Rettie, R. and Rayner, K. (2009). Eye movements and attention in reading, scene perception, and visual search. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology* 62 (8), 1457-1506.
- Reber, R. and N. Schwarz, N. (2001). The hot fringes of consciousness: Perceptual fluency and affect. *Consciousness & Emotion* 2 (2), 223–231.
- Reber, R. and N. Zupaneck (2002). Effects of processing fluency on estimates of probability and frequency. In: *Frequency processing and cognition*. Ed. by: P. Sedlmeier and T. Betsch. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, pp. 175–188.
- Schwarz, N. (2004). Metacognitive experiences in consumer judgment and decision making. *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 14 (4), 332–348.
- Reber, R., Schwarz, N., and P. Winkielman (2004a). Processing fluency and aesthetic pleasure: Is a beauty in the perceiver's processing experience? *Personality and Social Psychology Review* 8 (4), 364–382.
- Reber, R., Winkielman, P., and N. Schwarz (1998). Effects of perceptual fluency on affective judgments. *Psychological Science* 9 (1), 45–48.
- Reber, R., Wurtz, P., and T. D. Zimmermann (2004b). Exploring "fringe" consciousness: the subjective experience of perceptual fluency and its objective bases. *Consciousness and Cognition* 13 (1), 47–60.
- Rolls-Willson, G., (2007). The role of situational variables in online grocery shopping in the UK. *The Marketing Review*, 7(1): 89–106.
- San Martín, H. and Á. Herrero (2012). Influence of the user's psychological factors on the online purchase intention in rural tourism: Integrating innovativeness to the UTAUT framework. *Tourism Management*, 33(2): p. 341-350.
- Schifferstein, H. N., Howell, B. F., and S. C. Pont (2017). Colored backgrounds affect the attractiveness of fresh produce, but not it's perceived color. *Food Quality and Preference* (56), 173–180.
- Schwarz, N. (2015). Metacognition. In: *APA handbook of personality and social psychology*. Volume 1: Attitudes and social cognition. Ed. by: M. Mikulincer and P. R. Shaver. Washington, DC: APA, pp. 203–229.
- Schwarz, N. and G. L. Clore (1983). Mood, misattribution, and judgments of well-being: Informative and directive functions of affective states. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 45 (3), 513–523.
- Seiders, K., Voss, G. B., Godfrey, A. L. And Grewal D. 2007. Servcon: Development and Validation of a Multidimensional Service Convenience Scale, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 35(1): 144–56.

- Sevilla, J. and C. Townsend (2016). The space-to-product ratio effect: How interstitial space influences product an aesthetic appeal, store perceptions, and product preference. *Journal of Marketing Research* 53 (5), 665–681.
- Shapiro, S. (1999). When an ad's influence is beyond our conscious control: Perceptual and conceptual fluency effects caused by incidental ad exposure. *Journal of Consumer Research* 26 (1), 16– 36.
- Shapiro, S. A. and J. H. Nielsen (2013). What the blind eye sees: Incidental change detection as a source of perceptual fluency. *Journal of Consumer Research* 39 (6), 1202–1218.
- Song, H., and N. Schwarz (2009). If it's difficult to pronounce, it must be risky: Fluency, familiarity, and risk perception. *Psychological Science* 20 (2), 135-138.
- Song, S. S. and M. Kim (2012). Does more mean better? An examination of visual product presentation in e-retailing. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research* 13 (4), 345–355.
- Sreya, R. And Raveendran, P.T. (2017). Effect of shopping orientations on attitude towards online shopping - a multiple regression approach. *Management Insight*, 12(2): 1–7.
- Statista (2017). Share of consumers likely to buy groceries online in the United States from 2015 to 2017. Statista: The Statistic Portal. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/754815/onlinegrocery-consumer-share/> [Accessed: 2018, January 8].
- Steinmann, S., Kilian, T., and D. Brylla (2014). Experiencing products virtually: The role of vividness and interactivity in influencing mental imagery and user reactions. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS)*, <https://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2014/proceedings/HumanBehaviour/50/>.
- Stewart, D. W. 1981. The Application and Misapplication of Factor Analysis in Marketing Research. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1): 51–62.
- Stuart, E. W., Shimp, T. A., and R. W. Engle (1987). Classical conditioning of consumer attitudes: Four experiments in an advertising context. *Journal of Consumer Research* 14 (3), 334–349.
- Sunaga, T., Park, J., and C. Spence (2016). Effects of Lightness-Location Congruency on Consumers' Purchase Decision-Making. *Psychology & Marketing* 33 (11), 934–950.
- Szymanski, D. M., and R. T. Hise (2000). e-Satisfaction: An initial examination. *Journal of Retailing* 76 (3), 309–322.
- Tao, D., Tham, J. and Azam S. M. F. (2019). Voluntary Community Service Effectiveness among College Students in Tongren University, China. *European Journal of Social Science Studies*, 4(4): 156-173.
- Tarofder, A. K. and Azam, S. M. F. and Jalal, A. N. (2017), Operational or Strategic Benefits: Empirical Investigation of Internet Adoption in Supply Chain Management, *Management Research Review*, 40 (1): 28-52.

- Tarofder, A. K., Haque, A., Hashim, N., Azam, S. M. F. and Sherief, S. R. (2019). Impact of Ecological Factors on Nationwide Supply Chain Performance, *Ekoloji*, 28(107): 695-704.
- Tham, J., Yazid, M. S. A, Khatibi, A. A. and Azam, S. M. F. (2017), Internet and Data Security – Understanding Customer Perception on Trusting Virtual Banking Security in Malaysia. *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 2 (7): 186-207.
- Udriyah, U., Tham, J. and Azam, S. M. F. (2019). The Effects of Market Orientation and Innovation on Competitive Advantage and Business Performance of Textile SMEs, *Management Science Letters*, 9 (9): 1419-1428.
- Wedel, M., Pieters, R., and J. Liechty (2008). Attention switching during scene perception: How goals influence the time course of eye movements across advertisements. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied* 14 (2), 129–138.
- Wu, K., Vassileva, J., Zhao, Y., Noorian, Z., Waldner, W., and I. Adaji (2016). Complexity or simplicity? Designing product pictures for advertising in online marketplaces. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 28, 17–27. Brylla and Walsh / Isolated Product Depictions Twenty-Sixth European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS2018), Portsmouth,UK, 2018 16.
- Yoo, J. and M. Kim (2014). The effects of online product presentation on consumer responses: A mental imagery perspective. *Journal of Business Research* 67 (11), 2464–2472. *Commerce*, 2(2): p. 69-87.

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